

Drawing design specifications for plant root-inspired artificial diggers through DEM analysis

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Abstract— Plant roots are excellent soil diggers and can suggest efficient strategies for the movements of artificial soil penetrometers. In this study, we present a three-dimensional Discrete Element Model that was developed to simulate the penetration process of a bioinspired digger into soil. Specifically, we analyse a system that imitates characteristic movements of plant roots. Penetration in a granular cohesionless medium is simulated by mimicking axial and radial growths. We evaluate the performance of the system in terms of penetration pressure experienced, to determine the appropriate system size and actuation power requirements depending on the soil granularity. Furthermore, we compare the performance of the root-like digger with that achieved through traditional penetration methods, which involve externally applied force to push the probe into the soil. The results demonstrate the advantage of employing root-inspired strategies for movement in a granular medium and provide conditions that offer greater benefits.

Keywords—Soil exploration, bioinspired robotics, soil-robot interaction, DEM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underground exploration relies on technological solutions that are usually cumbersome, energy-demanding and intrusive [1]. During soil exploration, reducing the stresses perceived by the system is fundamental to increasing the drilling system stabilization, providing steerability and branching to explore wide areas and ensuring safety for the system, the operator, and the environment [2], [3]. In this context, robotic solutions play a crucial role in addressing these challenges [4], with great attention to bioinspired approaches [4, 5]. Bioinspired robotics proposes a new approach to developing sustainable and less invasive soil exploratory autonomous systems by examining how natural organisms accomplish similar tasks [5]. Among natural organisms, plant roots represent an interesting source of inspiration to develop unconventional autonomous systems able to penetrate dense medium [6,7]. Plant roots move into the soil by following environmental stimuli [8,9] and exploiting low friction paths to easily move into the soil [10]. Plant roots move by growing at the apical region [11-15] through cell division and elongation processes (Fig. 1a), which provide the required pressure (up to 1 MPa [16]) to penetrate soil successfully. The penetration strategy observed in plant roots inspired several burrowing and soil exploratory systems [6, 22]. By imitating the apical growth through a layer-by-layer addition of artificial material at the tip of a robotic artifact,

Sadeghi et al. [24] demonstrated that this strategy of motion benefits soil penetration by reducing lateral friction and, consequently, energy expenditure.

In addition to axial growth, plant roots expand in a radial direction. Despite biologically analyzing root radial growth being challenging [17-19], it has been assumed to induce cracks in the soil ahead of the root tip [20, 21], facilitating penetration.

In this study, we selected the Discrete Element Method (DEM) [25] to develop a three-dimensional (3-D) DEM numerical model for investigating the penetration requirements of a plant root-inspired digger for successfully exploring a cohesionless granular medium. In particular, we aim to understand the conditions in which axial and radial growth can benefit penetration and extract design specifications concerning probe size and power requirements for artificial soil explorers.

II. METHODOLOGY

The 3-D DEM numerical model was developed using the Yade software [26], which is an open-source framework comprising multiple functionalities to create DEM-based models with a granular soil domain following the sphere-based approach proposed by Cundall and Strack (1979) [27].

Our study considers a representative elementary volume of soil having a cubic shape with six rigid frictionless walls characterized by a side length $D_{chamber}$. The simulated soil consists of heterogeneously sized spherical particles having a median particle size D_{50} . The simulated root-like digger (Fig. 1b) comprises a cylindrical body with a diameter D_{root} and a conic tip with a base section diameter D_{root} and an aperture angle of 60° . Specifically, the cylindrical body includes a) an upper region, which remains fixed with respect to the surrounding medium (the green cylinder in Fig. 1b) and is modeled as a single rigid body, and b) a lower region (in red in Fig. 1b), which grows axially through the addition of new spherical particles with diameter D_{root} pushing downward the conic tip. Based on the outcomes of a Sensitivity Analysis (SA), the digger growth is executed at a rate of 1 m/s.

The inter-particles and digger-particle interactions were modeled using an elastic, perfectly plastic contact model with dry friction and rolling resistance to counteract the rolling effect experienced by the virtual soil not evident in real granular media.

Fig. 1. a) *Zea mays* root growing in agar medium with major zones highlighted. b) Sketch of the simulated root-like digger with highlighted the different root-like zones and domain parameters. c-e) Sketches of the three different analyses performed. c) Shows the conceptual implementation of apical growth. The red region is the newly added part at each growth step. d) Represents the penetration as performed by a traditional penetrometer pushed at the top (red part). e) The analysis of the radial growth is implemented with first axially elongating, then radially expanding until reaching a limiting diameter (Dthickened), and then axial elongating again.

During the penetration process, the intruder penetration performances were analyzed at steady-state conditions (i.e., at a depth where the average force reaches a mostly stable value) [28, 18]. In this condition, we extracted design specifications in terms of proper system diameter compared to soil granularity and actuation power requirements. Performances are evaluated based on the penetration pressure experienced only at the digger tip. This is because the digger shaft does not slide over the soil particles thanks to the plant-inspired apical growth.

In particular, we evaluated the digger penetration requirements varying the digger to median particle size ratio (D_{root}/D_{50}) from 0.03 to 15. For $D_{root}/D_{50} \gg 1$, the soil chamber to digger size ratio $D_{chamber}/D_{root}$ was set equal to 20 as from a SA performed on this parameter, aiming to find an acceptable solution to avoid boundary effects while reducing computational time. For $D_{root}/D_{50} \ll 1$, $D_{chamber}/D_{50}$ was kept constant at 136.

Finally, we tested the hypothesis that radial expansion can improve penetration performance by generating voids underneath. This analysis was performed by first penetrating with only axial growth up to a target depth, then stopping the axial growth and enlarging the diameter above the tip until reaching a pre-defined $D_{thickened}$ (we tested up to $1.5D_{root}$, $2D_{root}$, and $2.5D_{root}$). When $D_{thickened}$ is reached, axial growth is resumed. We evaluated the forces experienced during axial growth in dense and loose granular media.

III. RESULTS

Our analysis shows that the axial soil resistance pressure experienced by the tip has a characteristic fluctuating behavior around a mean value, which rises with increasing D_{root}/D_{50} . In particular, if $D_{root}/D_{50} \ll 1$, resistance forces exerted by the soil on the digger tend to a constant value. By contrast, when $D_{root}/D_{50} \gg 1$, the soil resistance pressure perceived by the digger tends to a constant value. This outcome strongly agrees with the pile foundation theory [30,31], which validates the reliability of our model.

Furthermore, we compared the performances of a plant root-like digger (i.e., penetrating using apical growth) to the ones of a traditional penetrometer (i.e., penetrating by being pushed externally from the top) in both cases with D_{root}/D_{50}

$\ll 1$ and $D_{root}/D_{50} \gg 1$. The penetration pressure required by a root-like system to successfully penetrate drops by 70.4 % when $D_{root}/D_{50}=0.1$, whereas it decreases by 7.7 % when $D_{root}/D_{50}=6.8$. The latter result might be found because when the soil particles are much smaller than the intruder size, there is much less opportunity to find a big pore where the system can move. However, both results demonstrate the advantage of employing apical growth with respect to a traditional penetration.

Investigations on radial growth in a dense medium provide that, during radial expansion, the pressures experienced in axial growth drop, reaching about 100% decrease with $D_{thickened} \geq 2D_{root}$. Specifically, for $D_{thickened} > 2D_{root}$, pressure reductions do not differ significantly from $D_{thickened} = 2D_{root}$, suggesting diminishing returns in gain of performance.

Moreover, after recovering axial growth upon radial expansion, the tip travels for a certain displacement (Δz) in a low-pressure regime that gradually increases until recovering the high regime obtained before applying radial expansion. For larger $D_{thickened}$, Δz is longer.

On the contrary, results in loose soil prove that implementing radial growth would be an energy loss since the high-regime pressure is recovered immediately after radial expansion. This effect is explained by the fact that the dense soil results dilatant, whereas the loose granular medium is contractant. In the first case, soil porosity increases below the tip during radial expansion, whereas in the second case, it diminishes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the development of a 3-D Discrete Element Model for simulating the penetration into cohesionless granular soil with heterogenous granules size of a plant root-like system, i.e., that moves via apical growth.

The soil axial resistance is evaluated as a function of the digger to median particle size ratio (D_{root}/D_{50}) to estimate the behavior of a) a given system penetrating in media having different granularities and b) systems having different sizes that penetrate a soil characterized by a certain granularity.

We obtained that, for all cases of D_{root}/D_{50} in between 0.03 and 15, the soil resistance experienced by the digger

oscillates around a mean value rising with increasing Droot/D50. For $Droot/D50 \gg 1$, the intruder tends to perceive a constant soil resistance pressure during penetration, in agreement with pile foundation theory. By contrast, when $Droot/D50 \ll 1$, the system needs to overcome soil resistance forces that tend to a constant value.

In addition, penetration performances of a root-like digger were compared to those of a traditional penetrometer for both small and big Droot/D50. Our outcomes highlighted that root-like diggers are always advantageous since they imply lower soil resistance during penetration, particularly when $Droot/D50 \ll 1$.

Finally, we verified that radial expansion can be advantageous in a dense medium, providing greater porosity underneath the tip, whereas in a loose medium, soil compacts and imposes more resistance.

As future perspectives, the developed numerical model can be adopted to investigate how penetration performances may be affected by other functionalities observed in plant roots (e.g., circumnutational movements) to understand if they could be advantageous for artificial exploratory systems.

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